

Deliverable 5.1

Project ID	654241
Project Title	A comprehensive and standardised e-infrastructure for analysing medical metabolic phenotype data
Project Acronym	PhenoMeNal
Start Date of the Project	1st September 2015
Duration of the Project	36 Months
Work Package Number	5
Work Package Title	Operations and Maintenance of PhenoMeNal GRID/Cloud
Deliverable Title	D5.1 Build System with continuous integration, providing development snapshots of PhenomeNal Virtual Machine Images
Delivery Date	M9
Work Package leader	UU
Contributing Partners	UU, IPB, EMBL-EBI, CEA, CRIMMP
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Abstract: This initial deliverable presents the setup, maintenance and security features of a shared Jenkins Instance for continuous integration in the PhenoMeNal project, as well as its place in the overall e-infrastructure.	

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1. Executive Summary

The PhenoMeNal grid/cloud infrastructure provides the foundation upon where data and analysis services can be easily discovered and used on scalable compute resources. It comprises the e-infrastructure as well as middleware for orchestrating analysis components and for enabling the functions in the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) developed in WP6 (PhenoMenal Virtual Research Community Gateway). Of high importance is the packaging of infrastructure resources and configurations to allow for easy setup on different types of systems. To this end, a Continuous Integration (CI) system has established up as a focal point of PhenoMeNal development to gather the building of all tools, package them into virtual machines or software containers, carry out unit testing, and publish the components to public repositories and dedicated PhenoMeNal repositories. The VRE can then discover and retrieve the published components for use in analysis workflows. PhenoMeNal has chosen a Jenkins installation as CI system, and has deployed an instance at <https://phenomenal-h2020.eu/jenkins/>. Currently the Jenkins system comprises 24 builds (projects) and 26 members of the consortium registered; this list will grow further during the project lifetime. In order to tighten security, we added a two-factor authentication mechanism for logging in and making changes to the Jenkins configuration.

In a distributed organization it is crucial to provide a focal point in development, and with a CI system PhenoMeNal has established a single point where all integrated tools can be surveyed and tested, both individually and together, before making them available to the VRE. This constitutes an important step towards a controlled development lifecycle and will greatly speed up continuous delivery of PhenoMeNal VRE and individual analysis tools, and reduce the risk of interoperable components.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

- Operation and maintenance of the GRID/cloud infrastructure.
- Maintenance and provisioning of the PhenoMeNal services in the PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure.

3. Detailed Report on Deliverable

3.1. Continuous integration in the context of PhenoMeNal

PhenoMeNal develops and integrates a large suite of software, containers and virtual machines. In this Deliverable we describe the Continuous Integration (CI) system set up as a central point for downloading source and data files, build software and tools, as well as assemble and package containers and virtual machines with functionality for testing the components individually and via integration tests. With a CI system, PhenoMeNal can automatically trigger builds when new commits are pushed to any of the dependent source code repositories (primarily Github), and notify developers if any of the unit tests fail. There will also be a possibility to add on a layer for testing interoperability between components, which will be explored and used in later stages of the project.

A strategic decision has been made in PhenoMeNal to build the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) as a Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) based on software containers that are orchestrated in an Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) environment with virtual machines that could be provided via a cloud computing provider or a local desktop computer or server. The necessary build scripts for the e-infrastructure middleware also need to be updated as underlying resources are changed; e.g. the base virtual machine images (VMI) on Amazon and Google Cloud are patched with the latest security updates on a weekly basis and the PhenoMeNal additions to these then need to be re-packaged and automatically tested ensuring that nothing has been broken during this process.

Figure 1: Overview of the Continuous Integration server in the PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure. The Jenkins instance retrieves source code and configuration files from repositories, builds the tools and assembles the virtual machine images (VMIs) and software containers, and carries out testing. The VMIs and containers are then pushed to a container repository, and are then available for download and deployment in PhenoMeNal VRE.

3.2. Implementation

PhenoMeNal has selected the CI system Jenkins (<https://jenkins.io/>), which is a proven system that provides all necessary functionality for building, testing, deploying, and automating a large variety of projects. The PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure will rely mostly on Docker container (<https://www.docker.com>) images for metabolomics/bioinformatics tools, workflow environments (such as Galaxy, <https://galaxyproject.org/>) and other running environments (such as Jupyter, <http://jupyter.org/>). These container images will run within container orchestration infrastructure (such as Kubernetes or Mesos). The source code for containers is managed by the tool provider, and PhenoMeNal requires all tools to be available under an open source license and in a publicly available source code repository (such as Github). PhenoMeNal also has set up an organization account in Github at <https://github.com/phnmnl> where organization-specific development is hosted.

3.3. Virtual infrastructure definitions

Virtual infrastructures in PhenoMeNal comprises compute nodes, networks, storage, middleware, software, workflows etc - all glued together into an environment (virtual research environment or VRE) where researchers have the resources and tools to carry out efficient and agile data analysis. The virtual infrastructures are defined in configuration files (sometimes referred to as *infrastructure-as-code*). These configuration files are made available in the PhenoMeNal github repository <https://github.com/phnmnl>, and can be used to in a straightforward way fire up a PhenoMeNal VRE on any IaaS providers, such as Google Cloud, Amazon, or private OpenStack systems. We will in the future explore unit testing frameworks for virtual infrastructures and cloud, such as Distributive (<https://github.com/CiscoCloud/distributive>).

3.4. Virtual Machine Images

Virtual Machine Images (VMIs) for the container orchestration and file system layers are built primarily using Packer, <https://www.packer.io/> and Ansible <https://www.ansible.com/>. The definition of these VMIs is available in version control systems in public repositories (github), from where our Jenkins server pulls the new versions and builds these VMIs. The built VMIs receive an incremented version, and are made publicly available on a URL, and the old versions are archived in a rolling manner so that previous versions can be used if desired.

3.5. Docker images

Dockerfile definitions and required files are stored in version control systems, from where the Jenkins server pulls these files to generate new versions of the Docker images. The newly built Docker images are pushed to the secure PhenoMeNal Docker registry and optionally to other public registries such as DockerHub

(<https://hub.docker.com/>). Execution of PhenoMeNal pipelines in the VRE, within container orchestration systems (we support both Mesosphere (<https://mesosphere.com/>) and Kubernetes (<http://kubernetes.io/>), triggers the download of the required Docker images from the PhenoMeNal Docker registry or other public Docker registries.

3.6. PhenoMeNal Jenkins Installation

The Jenkins CI server instance currently runs on the EBI EMBASSY Cloud (OpenStack), on an Ubuntu Trusty Server VMI, and runs Jenkins through the official docker container plus the following additional plugins installed:

- CloudBees Docker Build and Publish plugin
- Docker Commons Plugin
- Packer Plugin
- SAML 2.0 Two factor authentication Plugin

The PhenoMeNal Jenkins VMI was provisioned using Cloud-Init and the OpenStack API. Additionally, non-ephemeral disk is provided to this machine, to save the configuration/settings of the running Jenkins, so that if the docker container housing it needs to be restarted, the VMI needs to be restarted or the VMI stops non-gracefully and needs to be rebuilt from zero, the Jenkins settings (users, jobs, plugins, etc) are not lost.

Given that this CI server needs to build docker images, we have set up Jenkins slave machines for this purpose (using Ubuntu Trusty Server as well, with docker installed; provisioned through Cloud-Init and the OpenStack API). Figure 2 shows an overall schematic describing how the different parts interact. Figure 3 shows a screenshot of the Jenkins CI server, running on the EBI EMBASSY Cloud, which is available at <https://phenomenal-h2020.eu/jenkins/>.

Figure 2: The main components associated to the PhenoMeNal Jenkins Continuous Integration server. Docker containers are the main components being built by Jenkins, but VMIs are built using a similar procedure.

3.7. Building docker containers

Once a PhenoMeNal dockerfile is ready for producing an image, the developer of the dockerfile needs to either obtain credentials or ask a registered developer to set up the Job in Jenkins, so that the CI is aware of the location (git repository, branch, path, etc.) and other settings for the build (image name, owner, version, etc). This is normally done by duplication of an existing Job and changing the appropriate parts mentioned previously. The CI server uses the CloudBees Docker build and publish plugin for most docker jobs. After this is set up, the system takes care of the job on its own, as explained next. When a developer updates a dockerfile in the PhenoMeNal GitHub repository, the Docker image build is triggered automatically on a Jenkins slave machine (through hooks set up on Jenkins). If the Job is set to use a GitHub repository that is different to the PhenoMeNal one, then additional setup is required for the automatic trigger of docker image builds. This happens out of the box if the GitHub repository is owned by the PhenoMeNal organization on GitHub. Once successfully finished building the image, the Jenkins slave machine pushes it to our PhenoMeNal secure public Docker registry, available at <https://docker-registry.phenomenal-h2020.eu/>, and optionally to other public docker registries (like Docker Hub or quay.io). Figure 2 illustrates this flow as well. The PhenoMeNal docker registry requires credentials for pushing images (available for the

CI), but allows anonymous users to pull images without a password (public for pulling; private for pushing).

3.8. Building virtual machine images

Once PhenoMeNal developers have developed a well-tested Packer VMI building script, they create a Jenkins project for it. To execute Packer code for building VMIs, Jenkins uses the Packer Plugin and sends the building job to a Jenkins slave machine. Slave machines, as in the case of docker, have been provisioned with Packer and Ansible to be able to build VMIs. The VMI building process ends with Packer pushing the built image for different IaaS providers including Google Cloud Platform, Amazon Web Servers and OpenStack to publicly available URL, as well as the local OpenStack installation so that OpenStack can deploy VMs with those images. In the longer term, we expect to be able to push images to other private and public Cloud providers, including academic federated cloud providers including EGI.

3.9. Security

We extended Jenkins with a two-factor authentication for PhenoMeNal developers, provided for free by sasspass.com through SAML 2.0. This was implemented because Jenkins allows direct injection of shell commands, and building docker images requires root access for Jenkins. This risk of injection is partly mitigated as well by not building docker images on the same Jenkins machine but only on Jenkins slaves, which are separate machines with no private keys that would allow access to other machines in the tenancy (should anyone gain access to the slaves through injections). Connection is secured through HTTPS from the user to the proxy server that exposes the Jenkins machine, using free certificates obtained from Let's Encrypt(<https://letsencrypt.org>).

EBI EMBASSY Cloud provides snapshots for non-ephemeral volumes (this is where PhenoMeNal Jenkins data is stored; the same for the PhenoMeNal Docker registry) as backup mechanism, should anything happen to this storage. Updating the Jenkins docker instance is handled automatically on weekly basis using a recurrent schedule. The machine where Jenkins runs receives security updates automatically, and restarts at 4:00 AM GMT if needed, resuming as well the Jenkins docker image which runs Jenkins.

Figure 3: A screenshot of the public view of the PhenoMeNaL Jenkins Continuous Integration server. This can be seen live on your browser (no need to authenticate) [here](#). Blue spheres represent working builds.

3.10. Scalability

The CI server can be subject to a variable amount of load for building VMIs/docker images, and in the future also testing of containers (to check that the software in the container can do what it is supposed to do). On first instance, we rely on the ability of Jenkins to use Jenkins slaves, where the jobs are executed, within our OpenStack tenancy to be able to scale up should we need to process a higher amount of image builds. There are several options on Jenkins for hooking up a container orchestration system, which we could use in the future for dealing with very intensive container tests, should this become intractable for the slaves model.

3.11. Sustainability

The continuous integration service Jenkins is intended to serve as a central hub of development within PhenoMeNaL. Jenkins can integrate development from various

sources such as Github, Sourceforge or internal sources within PhenoMeNal. It allows quick but sophisticated overview of the development progress and allows for automatic building of VMIs and containers triggered by updates in the source code. From the PhenoMeNal-Jenkins we are able to upload new versions of containers to the central PhenoMeNal Docker registry and to the official Docker hub registry, which are then available to PhenoMeNal users and the central PhenoMeNal-VRE installation. An automated build and testing system is very important in order to streamline maintenance and ensure a sustainable development infrastructure in PhenoMeNal. Jenkins is a reliable solution proven in a large number of projects worldwide, and the key in PhenoMeNal to ensure working components over time is to have good test coverage for all projects - which is something that we will put large emphasis on in the remaining project lifetime. With sufficient tests, developers of individual components in PhenoMeNal will be continuously informed if any new updates break tests and hence interoperability within PhenoMeNal framework. Hence, the PhenoMeNal Jenkins will continue to serve PhenoMeNal infrastructure and users after the end of the project, with low maintenance costs.

3.12. Statistics

The CI server currently houses 24 build jobs (projects) and 26 registered developers from within the PhenoMeNal community. The number of build jobs will increase during the project as more tools, containers, VMIs and infrastructure definitions are developed. Some partners haven't yet finished their initial dockerfiles for their contributed tools, so when this is the case, it should mean an additional 7 to 8 additional build jobs. These include e.g. the NMR based tools from ICL and UoB, and several downstream packages for statistics etc from, amongst others, UL. Currently, all our docker images are building correctly and being pushed to the PhenoMeNal docker registry.

Project name	Description
bioc_docker_devel_metabolomics	The R BioConductor Metabolomics View docker image.
docker-batman	The BATMAN NMR data analysis tool based on R.
docker-galaxy-testing	A plain installation of GALAXY that is intended to be used for testing workflows and new components for Workflow4Metabolomics.
docker-metfamily	Docker port of MetFamily that helps identifying metabolites and groups them into

	metabolite clusters (“families”).
docker-metfrag-cli	The command line version of MetFrag, a tool for <i>in-silico</i> fragmentation for computer assisted identification of metabolite mass spectra.
docker-nmlmrconv	Convert NMR RAW vendor files to nmrML.
docker-xcms	The R tool XCMS for the analysis of MS data.
docker-rstudio	The RStudio Server + the whole Bioconductor + all the other relevant R-related Metabolomics packages.
docker_ex_batch_feature_removal	Feature removal implemented in R
docker_ex_blankfilter	Filtering component implemented in R
docker_ex_cv	CV-component in R
docker_ex_featuresselection	Feature selection component in R
docker_ex_log2transformation	Log2 transformation implemented in R
docker_ex_merger	Merger based on multiple samples
docker_ex_splitter	Splitter based on multiple samples
docker-ipo	MassIPO is a tool to calculate optimized parameters for XCMS runs through factorial analysis.
docker-lcmsmatching	Tool to annotate LC mass spectra, using an in-house database containing already annotated mass spectra and chromatographic retention times of molecules. Part of Workflow4Metabolomics .
docker-univariate	Univariate parametric and non-parametric hypothesis testing with correction for multiple testing.
docker-multivariate	PCA, PLS(-DA), and OPLS(-DA).
docker-biosigner	Discovery of significant signatures from omics data.

docker-openms	OpenMS
docker-pwiz	ProteoWizard
packer-snic-uppmax-mantl	VMI for MANTL VRE at Snic Science Cloud
vagrant-plainr	VMI for R and bioconductor

Table 1: Listing of the available PhenoMeNal-Jenkins project as of 2016-05-27.

4. Work Plan

4.1. Structure and Management of WP5 tasks

The WP5 is dedicated to “Service” activities within the PhenoMeNal Work plan.

Structure:

The details about the objectives and the description of work as broken down into tasks in WP5 is described in detail in the document of work and Grant Agreement (GA) of the project. Below is the summary of the tasks including subtasks related towards this deliverable:

T5.5: Operation and Maintenance of Continuous Integration system (UU)

We will set up and maintain a shared Jenkins (<http://jenkins-ci.org/>) instance which will be accessible to the PhenoMeNal partners. The Jenkins system will be configured to build, test, and package services and workflows to ensure adequate resources for all services to work as expected. The Jenkins system will retrieve the source code for developed tools from remote version control repositories (such as git or svn), compile and package tools, run automated unit- and integration tests, report all errors or inconsistencies. The actual tests will be developed by software and workflow developers in WP9. The task was broken down into 11 subtasks:

- Continuous Integration (CI) server (Jenkins) running on the Embassy Cloud infrastructure (openstack), based on a docker image https://hub.docker.com/_/jenkins/.
- CI server secured with authentication from users
- CI server proxied to be accessible from the outside: set openstack network rules and settings in the apache proxy machine exposed. Accessible at <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/jenkins/>
- CI server needs to be able to run both vagrant and docker, which normally requires root access.

- Authentication should use two-factor authentication system using saaspass.com free service.
- Access given to PhenoMeNal collaborators upon request
- Training and support to PhenoMeNal collaborators on Jenkins via direct communication, chat and email
- Vagrant and docker images building allowed through the use of dedicated slaves machines within the EMBASSY Cloud infrastructure.
- Local docker registry set up on the EMBASSY Cloud, to store docker images produced. This runs on a CoreOS machine, and receives pushed images from the docker/CI slaves. It has a dedicated non-ephemeral volume for storing docker images. The registry itself runs on docker.
- Docker IPO image builds correctly and is pushed to local docker registry machines.
- Pre-build virtual infrastructure configurations using Packer.

Coordination and management of the activities:

The WP5 is led by Uppsala University who is responsible for the coordination of the planning of work and related deliverables. The tasks for this deliverable were distributed between EMBL-EBI (WP1 and WP6 lead), IPB (WP9 lead) and UU (WP5 lead) and were monitored using dedicated Google hangouts. The progress was tracked using Pivotal Tracker- an Agile project management tool (see figure 4).

Contained In PhenoMeNal

D5.1 - Build System with continuous integration, providing development snapshots of PhenoMeNal Virtual Machine Images

DESCRIPTION (edit)
UU - M9

LABELS
embi-ebi | ipb | m9 | uu | wp5 | year1

TASKS (9/9)

- Continuous Integration (CI) server (Jenkins) running on the EMBASSY Cloud infrastructure (openstack), based on a docker image https://hub.docker.com/_/jenkins/. This runs on top of Ubuntu 14.04 LTS Cloud image, with a non-ephemeral volume for storing settings (which means that both the microservice or the VM can be restarted without losing settings).
- CI Server secured with authentication from users
- CI Server proxied to be accessible from the outside: set openstack network rules and settings in the apache proxy machine exposed. Accessible at <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/jenkins/>
- CI Server needs to be able to run both vagrant and docker, which normally requires root access. Find a solution for this.
- Given the root access needs, the authentication from users was changed to a two way authentication system using saaspass.com free service. Users now can only access with dynamic authentication based on SAASPass.
- Access given to collaborators that requested it (IPB and Uppsala so far).
- Vagrant and docker images building allowed through the use of dedicated slaves machines within the EMBASSY Cloud infrastructure. On these machines, the user that jenkins uses is on the root access group, but these machines are not accessible from the outside of the tenancy through SSH or any other protocol but through the use of jenkins. These machines use special private/public keys and cannot run commands back on the jenkins machine, nor have ssh keys to access any machine in the tenancy. Currently, these slaves run on ubuntu 14.04, but might be good to move them to CoreOS if vagrant works there.
- Local docker registry set up on the EMBASSY Cloud, to store docker images produced. This runs on a CoreOS machine, and receives pushed images from the docker/CI slaves. It has a dedicated non-ephemeral volume for storing docker images. The registry itself runs on docker.
- docker IPO image builds correctly and is pushed to local docker registry machines

STORY TYPE: Feature
POINTS: 3 Points
STATE: Accepted on 25 May 2016
REQUESTER: OS Ola Spjuth
OWNERS: OS PM
FOLLOW THIS STORY: (3 followers)
Updated: 21 minutes ago

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DOC

Figure 4: Screenshot from the Pivotal Tool to show progress in terms of D5.1

Utilization of resources:

Total person month (PM) allotted: 204

Contribution from partners in terms of total PM utilized:

PMs Per Partners	UU:3	IPB: 3	EMBL-EBI: 2	CRIMMP: 1	CEA: 2
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5. Delivery and Schedule

The deliverable was submitted on time.

6. Conclusion:

The PhenoMeNal consortium has established a Jenkins system as a continuous integration system, providing a focal point in development and integration of tools. The system collects the source code of all developments in PhenoMeNal and allows for testing and publishing of all components to PhenoMeNal repositories. The system is in use by the consortium, as of 2016-05-27 had 24 projects and 26 registered users, and will continue to serve as a development and testing hub for the PhenoMeNal ecosystem.